

Technische
Universität
Braunschweig

Design for Change - Software Engineering to the rescue

A workshop on sustainable software engineering for scientists

Center for Mechanics, Uncertainty and Simulation in Engineering (MUSEN)

Who are we?

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Organizational matters

- Please mute your microphone while you are only listening
- If you have any questions please **draw attention by saying “Question”**
- When you are speaking please turn on your camera (if possible)
- We will have short breaks approx. every 1 to 1½ hours

Agenda

- Part 1 - Requirements and characteristics of **maintainable and sustainable research software**
- Part 2 - **Software Development Principle and Practices** that contribute to high-quality software design
- Part 3 – Design Patterns **hands-on session**

Which programming language do you prefer?

- a) C++
- b) Java
- c) Python
- d) Matlab
- e) R
- f) other

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How experienced are you?

- a) I have zero experience
- b) I have just a little experience
- c) I feel comfortable in programming
- d) I'm an expert
- e) I would rather not say

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One of the first scientific software developers

<https://bit.ly/3kYfXWR>

One of the first scientific software developers

“One of our difficulties will be the maintenance of an **appropriate discipline**, so that we **do not lose track of what we are doing.**”

- 1947

[Lecture to London Mathematical Society, February 20, 1947]

IT WORKED
yesterday

[photo: pixabay.com]

“ The art of programming is the art of organizing complexity. ”

Edsker W. Dijkstra

[Notes On Structured Programming, Edsker W. Dijkstra, 1970]

[Frederick P. Brooks, No Silver Bullet: Essence and Accidents of Software Engineering, 1987]

“The function of good software is to make the complex appear to be simple.”

Grady Booch

Software provides the ultimate flexibility ...

Relationships - Dependencies - Strong Coupling

Motivation

Publications relying on software

2 / 3rds

of papers indicate
software reliance in 2017

<https://bit.ly/37XEJ2u>

The typical scientific developer

- highly educated
- finds it easy to learn programming languages (university courses and/or self educated)
- no formal education in software engineering
- no reputation for developing software
- software itself has no value - only a tool for domain specific research
- doesn't see her- or himself as a software developer
- 70% of male and only 30% of female

Growing demands on scientific software

- increasing complexity (e.g. multi physics, multiple groups)
- longer life span (base your work on the work of others)
- reproducible and verifiable results

Growth in technology vs. software development paradigms

¹[John McCarthy, Recursive Functions of Symbolic Expressions and Their Computation by Machine, 1960]

²[Kristen Nygaard, Ole-Johan Dahl, The development of the SIMULA languages, 1978]

³[Edsger W. Dijkstra, Go To Statement Considered Harmful, 1968]

In accordance to Wirth's law one can argue:

“Software systems grow faster in size and complexity than methods to handle complexity are invented.”

[Niklaus Wirth, "A Plea for Lean Software", 1995]

Productivity Crisis

- floating point performance is constantly rising
- time-to-solution is inceasing
- scientists spend 50% of the time finding bugs

[P. Prabhu, A Survey of the Practice of Computational Science, 2011]

Design Stamina Hypothesis - <https://bit.ly/2A64CAR>

“The only way to go **fast** is to go **well**.”

Robert C. Martin

Credibility Crisis

Questionable reliability, accuracy, reproducibility and verifiability of the results ...

18 April 2013, 12:31 CEST

FAQ: Reinhart, Rogoff, and the Excel Error That Changed History

By Peter Coy

PHOTOGRAPH BY GREGOR SCHUSTER

SCIENTIFIC PUBLISHING

A Scientist's Nightmare: Software Problem Leads to Five Retractions

Until recently, Geoffrey Chang's career was on a trajectory most young scientists only dream about. In 1999, at the age of 28, the protein crystallographer landed a faculty position at the prestigious Scripps Research Institute in San Diego, California. The next year, in a ceremony at the White House, Chang received a Presidential Early Career Award for Scientists and Engineers, the country's highest honor for young researchers. His lab generated a stream of high-profile papers detailing the molecular structures of important proteins embedded in cell membranes.

Then the dream turned into a nightmare. In September, Swiss researchers published a paper in *Nature* that cast serious doubt on a protein structure Chang's group had described in a 2001 *Science* paper. When he investigated, Chang was horrified to discover that a homemade data-analysis program had flipped two columns of data, inverting the electron-density map from which his team had derived the final protein structure. Unfortunately, his group had used the program to analyze data for

Papers in economics 'not reproducible'

Fears that discipline is particularly susceptible to statistical 'hacking' of data to gain a positive result

October 21, 2015

By David Matthews

Twitter: @DavidMJourno

At least half of papers in economics are

Percent of papers

t.

cludes.

Sciences and a 2005 *Science* paper, described EmrE, a different type of transporter protein.

Crystallizing and obtaining structures of five membrane proteins in just over 5 years was an incredible feat, says Chang's former postdoc adviser Douglas Rees of the California Institute of Technology in Pasadena. Such proteins are a challenge for crystallographers because they are large, unwieldy, and notoriously difficult to coax into the crystals needed for x-ray crystallography. Rees says determination was at the root of Chang's success: "He has an incredible drive and work ethic. He really pushed the field in the sense

of getting things to crystallize that no one else had been able to do." Chang's data are good, Rees says, but the faulty software threw everything off.

Ironically, another former postdoc in Rees's lab, Kaspar Locher, exposed the mistake. In the 14 September issue of *Nature*, Locher, now at the Swiss Federal Institute of Technology in Zurich, described the structure of an ABC transporter called Sav1866 from *Staphylococcus aureus*. The structure was dramatically—and unexpectedly—different from that of MsbA. After pulling up Sav1866 and Chang's MsbA from *S. typhimurium* on a computer screen, Locher says he realized in minutes that the MsbA structure was inverted. Interpreting the "hand" of a molecule is always a challenge for crystallographers,

2001 *Science* paper, which described the structure of a protein called MsbA, isolated from the bacterium *Escherichia coli*. MsbA belongs to a huge and ancient family of molecules that use energy from adenosine triphosphate to transport molecules across cell membranes. These so-called ABC transporters perform many

Flipping fiasco. The structures of MsbA (purple) and Sav1866 (green) overlap little (left) until MsbA is inverted (right).

<https://go.nature.com/2DgtDKR>

Birth of Software Engineering discipline in 1968

[Naur, Software Engineering: Report of a Conference Sponsored by the NATO Science Committee, Garmisch, Germany, 1968]

Start caring about your code

“Clean code always looks like
it was written by someone who cares.”

Michael Feathers

[Robert C. Martin, Clean Code: A Handbook of Agile Software Craftsmanship, 2008]

Software Entropy - Broken Window Effect

Broken window effect: <https://bit.ly/2BddXYh>

[A. Hunt, The Pragmatic Programmer: From Journeyman to Master, 1999]

The Boy Scout Rule

“Leave the campground cleaner than you found it.”

[Robert C. Martin, Clean Code: A Handbook of Agile Software Craftsmanship, 2008]

It's all about concepts...

It needs more than knowing a language to be a successful author!

External and Internal Software Quality

Two Categories of Quality

- external and internal quality factors

External Quality Factors

- aim to the needs of a user

Internal Quality Factors

- aim to the needs of the developers

Implicit dependencies of several quality factors prevent maximization of all factors.

Engineering task: Optimal balancing of quality goals.

[James McCall, Factors in Software Quality, Technical Report, General Electric, 1977]

External Quality Factors - J. McCall, 1977

- **Correctness** - The degree to which a system is free from faults in its specification, design, and implementation.
- **Usability** - The ease with which users can learn and use a system.
- **Efficiency** - Minimal use of system resources, including memory and execution time.
- **Reliability** - The ability of a system to perform its required functions under stated conditions whenever required—having a long mean time between failures.
- **Integrity** - The degree to which a system prevents unauthorized or improper access to its programs and its data.
- **Adaptability** - The extent to which a system can be used, without modification, in applications or environments other than those for which it was originally designed.
- **Accuracy** - The degree to which a system, as built, is free from error, especially with respect to quantitative outputs. Accuracy differs from correctness; it is a determination of how well a system does the job it's built for rather than whether it was built correctly.
- **Robustness** - The degree to which a system continues to function in the presence of invalid inputs or stressful environmental conditions.

Internal Quality Factors - J. McCall, 1977

“The key to achieving these external factors is in the internal ones.”

– B. Meyer, 1988

- **Maintainability** - The ease with which you can modify a software system to change or add capabilities, improve performance, or correct defects.
- **Flexibility** - The extent to which you can modify a system for uses (or environments) other than those for which it was specifically designed.
- **Portability** - The ease with which you can modify a system to operate in an environment different from that for which it was specifically designed.
- **Reusability** - The extent to which and the ease with which you can use parts of a system in other systems.
- **Readability** - The ease with which you can read and understand the source code of a system, especially at the detailed-statement level.
- **Testability** - The degree to which you can unit-test and system-test a system; the degree to which you can verify that the system meets its requirements.
- **Understandability** - The ease with which you can comprehend a system at both the system-organizational and detailed-statement levels. Understandability has to do with the coherence of the system at a more general level than readability does.

[Bertrand Meyer, Object-Oriented Software Construction, 1988]

Quality characteristics valued by scientists – survey by J. Carver, 2007

- functional correctness
- performance
- portability
- maintainability

[Jeffrey Carver, Software Development Environments for Scientific and Engineering Software: A Series of Case Studies, 2007]

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What do you value the most?

- a) functional correctness
- b) performance
- c) portability
- d) maintainability

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Traditional vs. Agile Processes

Design
cheap

Product
expensive

[Jack W. Reeves, Code as Design: Three Essays, 2005]

Traditional vs. Agile Processes

```
1 define([
2   'can',
3   'models/account',
4   'controls/dashboard/dashboard',
5   'controls/misc/titlebar',
6   'toastr',
7   'moment',
8   'utils/helpers'
9 ], function(can, Account, Dashboard, Titlebar,
10  ) {
11   return can.Control.extend({
12     defaults: new can.Map({
13       success: null,
14       error: null,
15       username: null,
16       password: null
17     })
18  }, {
19    init: function() {
```

Design
expensive

Product
cheap

[photo: pixabay.com]

Evolution of costs for Hardware vs. Software

[Barry W. Boehm, Software and its impact: A quantitative assessment, 1973]

Traditional vs. Agile Processes

Waterfall

Agile

Project Timeline

Quality characteristics valued by scientists – survey by J. Carver, 2007

- functional correctness
- performance
- portability
- maintainability

[Jeffrey Carver, Software Development Environments for Scientific and Engineering Software: A Series of Case Studies, 2007]

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The one constant in **Software** development is

CHANGE

<https://bit.ly/3BGi1cU>

Object Oriented Programming – It's all about messages

Dependencies make changes difficult

Dependencies propagate change

Dependencies propagate change

Dependencies propagate change

Dependencies propagate change

“Design for **change by managing **dependencies**.”**

Low cohesion

Low cohesion

High cohesion

Metrics - Yourdon und Constantine, 1979

Use **Coupling** and **Cohesion** as Metrics to evaluate the quality of the design with regard to the impact and the reach of changes.

Coupling = Measure of Strength of the Relationship of two or more components.

A high Coupling causes systems, which are complicated to understand, to change or even to fix. Changes in a module often lead to a cascade of changes in other tightly coupled modules.

Cohesion = Degree of how well the elements of a module relate/fit together.

Random Cohesion = non-relating Abstractions are grouped together. [=> worst case]

High functional Cohesion = the sum of elements which form a consistent and clearly defined Behavior. Changes regarding a specific Behavior are easily performed, since they are ideally affecting a single element.

The Goal of the Design should therefore simultaneously aim for a **preferably high cohesion and low coupling** of its components.

[E. Yourdon and L.L. Constantine, Structured Design: Fundamentals of a Discipline of Computer Program and Systems Design, 1979]

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Design Smells

Symptoms of poor design

Rigidity – The system is difficult to change.

Fragility – The system is easy to break.

Immobility – The system is difficult to reuse.

Viscosity – It is difficult to do the right thing.

Needless Complexity – Overdesign.

Needless Repetition – Copy / Paste Development.

Opacity – The systems design is hard to understand.

These symptoms are similar in nature to code smells, but are at a higher level. They are smells that pervade the overall structure of the software rather than a small section of code.

[Robert C. Martin, Agile Principles, Patterns, and Practices, 2003]

Another metric for code quality

The ONLY VALID MEASUREMENT
OF CODE QUALITY: WTFs/MINUTE

<https://bit.ly/2VWkvBA>

» No Silver Bullet «

Software Development is a **non-deterministic** process – McConnell, 2004

Clearly, there is no magic, **no “silver bullet”** (F. P. Brooks, 1987) that can unfailingly lead the software engineer down the path from requirements to the implementation of a complex software system, which reflects a high-quality design on the other hand.

Software Design and Software Development are **evolutionary processes** which demand for an **incremental and iterative approach**.

There are “no” norms nor standards, which assure the quality of development.

Software Design is a **heuristic process** – Quality is mainly achieved by cautiously applying proven **Principles, Patterns and Practices**.

[Steve McConnell, Code Complete, Second Edition, 2004]

[Frederick P. Brooks, No Silver Bullet: Essence and Accidents of Software Engineering, 1987]

Complexity

“There is an inherent complexity in software systems that works against the software quality.”

– Dijkstra, 1972

Causes of Complexity (Booch et al., 2007):

- complexity of the problem domain
- difficulty of managing the development process
- flexibility possible through software
- problems of characterizing the behavior of discrete systems

Problems evolving in scope, result in continuously growing complexity of software systems. Complexity does not increase linearly. The more complex a system gets, the higher its possibility of failure gets. The task of designing high-quality software consists in managing its complexity.

[Edsger W. Dijkstra, The humble programmer, 1972]

[Grady Booch et al., Object-oriented analysis and design with applications, 2007]

Basic Concepts of Organized Complexity

“...the maximum number of chunks of information that an individual can handle simultaneously is on the order of seven, plus or minus two.”

– G. A. Miller, 1956

Decomposition: “divide et impera” (divide and conquer) – When designing a complex software system, it is essential to decompose it into smaller and smaller parts, each of which we may then refine independently.

Abstraction: “We (humans) have developed an exceptionally powerful technique for dealing with complexity. We abstract from it. Unable to master the entirety of a complex object, we choose to *ignore its inessential details*, dealing instead with the generalized, idealized model of the object” (W. Wulf ,1980)

Hierarchy: Another way to increase the semantic content of individual chunks of information is by explicitly recognizing the class and object hierarchies within a complex software system. By classifying objects into groups of related abstractions (e.g., kinds of plant cells versus animal cells), we come to explicitly distinguish the common and distinct properties of different objects, which further helps us to master their inherent complexity (A. Goldberg, 1984).

[George A. Miller, The Magical Number Seven, Plus or Minus Two: Some Limits on Our Capacity for Processing Information, 1956]

Object-orientation vs. complexity

Object-orientation (OO) is an approved paradigm to **organize the complexity of software**.

The methods of object-oriented analysis (OOA) and design (OOD) provide an engineering approach, which leads from the specific requirements to its software implementation.

The general procedure is based on principles of **modularization (decomposition), encapsulation, abstraction and hierarchy**.

Managing complexity with Object Oriented Programming

In the 1980s Alan Kay introduced the term „Object Oriented Programming“.

An OO Language should at least support the following three key principles:

- **Encapsulation**
- **Inheritance**
- **Polymorphism**

Object Oriented Programming - Encapsulation

Who's to blame?

- a) The circle
- b) The caller
- c) Both
- d) None of them

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Your PC ran into a problem and needs to restart. We're just collecting some error info, and then we'll restart for you.

If you'd like to know more, you can search online later for this error: ALWAYS_LOOK_ON_THE_BRIGHT_SIDE_OF_LIFE

Keep in mind!

An object is responsible to guarantee it's state is valid!

Object Oriented Programming - Encapsulation

Object Oriented Programming - Inheritance

crow

nightingale

eagle

hawk

duck

The Birdwatcher App

Object Oriented Programming - Inheritance

Object Oriented Programming - Inheritance

Object Oriented Programming - Inheritance

Object Oriented Programming - Inheritance

Classes can be specializations of other classes. That means classes can be in hierarchical order by inheriting properties and behavior of higher ranked classes.

Lower ranked classes can specialize (override) or extend higher classes.

On code level Inheritance may be used to **avoid redundancy** by allowing code reuse.

Inheritance enables Polymorphism!

Object Oriented Programming - Polymorphism

- Generally, the ability to have different individuals of a species.
(...also in Biology, Chemistry)
- In object-oriented programming, polymorphism refers to a programming language's ability of objects to react differently to one and the same message depending on their class.
(Technically, this is achieved by redefining methods in derived classes - Inheritance)
- One may also speak of the autonomy or independence of objects.

Polymorphism - Ant Hill

Polymorphism – All are ants

Polymorphism – Queen is managing the tribe (Core Unit)

Polymorphism - Worker Ant

Polymorphism – Soldier Ant

Polymorphism – Nurse Ant

Polymorphism – Queen doesn't know specific ants

Polymorphism – Queen only knows ants

Queen knows that ants understand the message: „DO YOUR JOB!“

All ants react differently to the message according to their subtype

Polymorphism – Ready for Evolution - SkyDriver Ant

Polymorphism – Ready for Evolution - SkyDriver Ant

Polymorphism – Queen Ant is not affected by change

Object Oriented Programming - Polymorphism

30W

Energy Saving

LED

More to come!

Object Oriented Programming - Polymorphism

Object Oriented Programming - Polymorphism

Principles of object-oriented Design

SOLID

Software Development is not a Jenga game

Principles of object-oriented Design

S.O.L.I.D. Principles

- **S**ingle Responsibility Principle (SRP)
- **O**pen-Closed Principle (OCP)
- **L**iskov Substitution Principle (LSP)
- **I**nterface Segregation Principle (ISP)
- **D**ependency Inversion Principle (DIP)

...Guidelines (no laws) for object-oriented design!

[Robert C. Martin, Agile Principles, Patterns, and Practices, 2003]

Single Responsibility Principle (SRP)

– Tom DeMarco [79]

SINGLE RESPONSIBILITY PRINCIPLE

Just Because You Can, Doesn't Mean You Should

Single Responsibility Principle (SRP)

– Tom DeMarco [79]

***Single Responsibility Principle –
Each class should only have one reason to change.***

Each Responsibility = Reason to change.

Changes also affect depending classes

Changes have to be made to depending classes

Possible failing behavior of depending classes (to be tested)

In C++ depending classes have to be recompiled unnecessarily after changes.

[Tom DeMarco, Structured Analysis and System Specification, 1979]

Single Responsibility Principle (SRP)

– Tom DeMarco [79]

Example – Violation of SRP:

Single Responsibility Principle (SRP)

– Tom DeMarco [79]

Solution:

Open-Closed Principle (OCP)

- Bertrand Meyer, 1988

OPEN CLOSED PRINCIPLE

Open Chest Surgery Is Not Needed When Putting On A Coat

[Bertrand Meyer, Object-Oriented Software Construction, 1988]

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Open-Closed Principle (OCP)

- Bertrand Meyer, 1988

Open for Extension, closed for modifications.

A module should be open for extensions, but closed for modifications.

Principle ensures extensions of components **without** changing the source code of the specific component.

Tool: **Polymorphism**

Encapsulation of *volatile* and *non-volatile* Code (in Base Classes)

Abstract Core of the application remains **untouched**.

Open-Closed Principle (OCP)

- Bertrand Meyer, 1988

--shapes.py-----

```
class Circle:
    def __init__(self, radius=1.0):
        self._radius: float = radius

    @property
    def radius(self) -> float:
        return self._radius

class Square:
    def __init__(self, length=1.0):
        self._length: float = length

    @property
    def length(self) -> float:
        return self._length
```

--app.py-----

```
def _draw_circle(radius):
    print(f"Draw circle with radius: {radius}.")

def _draw_square(length):
    print(f"Draw square with side length: {length}.")

class Application:
    def __init__(self, shapes) -> None:
        self._shapes = shapes

    def draw_all_shapes(self) -> None:
        for shape in self._shapes:
            if type(shape) is Circle:
                _draw_circle(shape.radius)
            if type(shape) is Square:
                _draw_square(shape.length)
```

volatile | non volatile

Open-Closed Principle (OCP)

- Bertrand Meyer, 1988

--shapes.py-----

```
class Circle(Shape):
    def __init__(self, radius=1.0):
        self._radius: float = radius

    def draw(self):
        print(f"Draw circle with radius: {self.radius}.")

class Square(Shape):
    def __init__(self, length=1.0):
        self._length: float = length

    def draw(self):
        print(f"Draw square with side length: {self.length}.")

class Rectangle(Shape):
    def __init__(self, side_a=1.0, side_b=1.0):
        ...
```

--shape_abc.py-----

```
class Shape(ABC):
    @abstractmethod
    def draw(self):
        pass
```

--app.py-----

```
class Application:
    def __init__(self, shapes: List[Shape]) -> None:
        self._shapes: List[Shape] = shapes

    def draw_all_shapes(self) -> None:
        for shape in self._shapes:
            shape.draw()
```

volatile : non volatile

Open-Closed Principle (OCP)

- Bertrand Meyer, 1988

--shapes.py-----

```
class Circle(Shape):
    def __init__(self, radius=1.0):
        self._radius: float = radius

    def draw(self):
        print(f"Draw circle with radius: {self.radius}.")

class Square(Shape):
    def __init__(self, length=1.0):
        self._length: float = length

    def draw(self):
        print(f"Draw square with side length: {self.length}.")

class Rectangle(Shape):
    def __init__(self, side_a=1.0, side_b=1.0):
        ...
```

--shape_abc.py-----

```
class Shape(ABC):
    @abstractmethod
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class Application:
    def __init__(self, shapes: List[Shape]) -> None:
        self._shapes: List[Shape] = shapes

    def draw_all_shapes(self) -> None:
        for shape in self._shapes:
            shape.draw()
```

volatile : non volatile

Open-Closed Principle (OCP)

- Bertrand Meyer, 1988

Liskov Substitution Principle (LSP)

- Barbara Liskov, 1987

LISKOV SUBSTITUTION PRINCIPLE

If It Looks Like A Duck, Quacks Like A Duck, But Needs Batteries - You Probably Have The Wrong Abstraction

[Barbara Liskov, Data Abstraction and Hierarchy, 1987]

Liskov Substitution Principle (LSP)

- Barbara Liskov, 1987

Liskov Substitution Principle

Type T' is a Subtype of T , if objects of Type T can be exchanged by objects of Type T' without any limitations.

Tight relationship to Inheritance and `virtual/abstract` methods

Simple Example:

A driver of a BMW shouldn't be surprised, if he tries to drive a VW.

(Since both are cars and should work in kind of the same way, when trying to interact with similar functions.)

Liskov Substitution Principle (LSP)

- Barbara Liskov, 1987

Example – Violation of LSP

- Situation:
Class `Rectangle` is existing.
Class `Square` is needed.
- Inheritance seems right:
A `Square` **IS** a `Rectangle`

What do you think – is a square a rectangle?

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Liskov Substitution Principle (LSP)

- Barbara Liskov, 1987

```
class Rectangle:
    def __init__(self, height=1.0, width=1.0):
        self._height: float = height
        self._width: float = width

    def set_height(self, height: float):
        self._height = height

    def set_width(self, width: float):
        self._width = width

    def area(self) -> float:
        return self._height * self._width
```

First doubts

- properties of Rectangle: 2 (height & width)
required properties of Square: 1
- ok, memory is cheap...

Liskov Substitution Principle (LSP)

- Barbara Liskov, 1987

```
class Square(Rectangle):  
    def __init__(self, width=1.0):  
        self._height = width  
        self._width = width  
  
    def set_height(self, height: float):  
        self._height = height  
        self._width = height  
  
    def set_width(self, width: float):  
        self._width = width  
        self._height = width
```

Further doubts

- properties: height & width
- names aren't suitable
- height and width have to be consistent

Liskov Substitution Principle (LSP)

- Barbara Liskov, 1987

```
def foo(r: Rectangle) {  
    r.set_width(5)  
    r.set_height(4)  
    if r.area() != 20:  
        print("Bad area!")  
}
```

Unpreventable Error:

legitimate assumption for Rectangle:

If height is changed, the width stays untouched!

But wrong polymorphic behavior of Square!

Liskov Substitution Principle (LSP)

- Barbara Liskov, 1987

Violation of the Open Closed Principle (OCP)

Using the `Square` class introduces a dependency to the subtype of `Rectangle`!

```
def foo(r: Rectangle) {  
    r.set_width(5)  
    r.set_height(4)  
    if r.area() != 20 and not isinstance(r, Square):  
        print("Bad area!")  
}
```

Conclusion:

Although a `Square` is a `Rectangle` in a geometric sense, this isn't true in the sense of software (polymorphism)!

Dependency Inversion Principle (DIP)

Dependency Inversion Principle (DIP)

Dependency Inversion Principle

- a) *High-level modules should not depend on low-level modules. Both should depend on abstractions.*
- b) *Abstractions should not depend upon details. Details should depend upon abstractions.*

But: If a concrete class is not going to change very often, and no other similar derivatives are going to be created, it does very little harm to depend on it.

Dependency Inversion Principle (DIP)

Example – Violation of DIP

Button is directly dependent on *Lamp*.

Changes in *Lamp* have a direct impact on *Button*.

Button can only control objects of *Lamp*.

Button can't be reused.

Dependency Inversion Principle (DIP)

Solution

Button is now depending on an interface called ButtonServer.

Changes in Lamp won't influence the Button.

Button can be reused.

Button can control any object which implements the interface of ButtonServer.

Inverted direction of dependency

Interface Segregation Principle (ISP)

Interface Segregation Principle (ISP)

Interface Segregation Principle

Covers the drawbacks of broadly defined interfaces

Classes with non-coherent interfaces

Problem:

Dependency of the calling object to methods, which it doesn't need know because it isn't using them.
Changes to an interface are concerning **every** object knowing that interface.

Solution:

(Coherent) Segregation of methods to multiple interfaces for the specific calling objects.

Dynamic languages aren't affected.

Interface Segregation Principle (ISP)

Interface Segregation Principle (ISP)

Books

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Introduction to Software Design Patterns

Design Patterns

Origin in architecture (Similarity of structures and styles)*

From architectural patterns to patterns of software design:

1995 GoF: “Design Patterns: Elements of Reusable Object-Oriented Software”**

1. Transferred the idea of patterns to software design.
2. Defined a structure to categorize the patterns.
3. 23 patterns were categorized.
4. Presented object-oriented strategies and approaches based on design patterns.

* Christopher Alexander: The Timeless Way of Building, 1979

** Gang of Four (GoF) Erich Gamma, Richard Helm, Ralph Johnson, John Vlissides

Design Patterns

- Reliable solutions / strategies for repeating design problems in software engineering
- The description of a design pattern follows certain rules*:
 - description of a **problem**
 - description of a **solution**
 - structure, elements, interactions
 - **discussion**
 - advantages / disadvantages / dependencies
 - source code **examples**
 - related design patterns
- independent of a specific programming language

* Erich Gamma, Richard Helm, Ralph Johnson, John Vlissides, Design Patterns, 1995

What Design Patterns are not:

- Not a “one-size-fits-all” solution. You need to adapt it to your context.
- No algorithms - algorithms solve problems (search, sort etc.) and are less flexible in their implementation
- Design patterns are no magical cure! When applying a pattern creative talent is still needed
- Design patterns are no frameworks or libraries. Frameworks and libraries provide reusable code. Design patterns only provide templates for solutions.

Why would you care about design patterns?

Tyranny of the Details: The Carpenter and the drawers

How do you think we should build these drawers?

Well, I think we should make the joint by cutting straight down the wood, and then cut back up 45 degrees, and then going straight back down, and then back up the other way 45 degrees, And then going straight back down, and then...

Details may cause confusion!

Try to figure out, what they're talking about!

Why would you care about design patterns?

Tyranny of the Details: The Carpenter and the drawers

How do you think we should build these drawers?

Should we use *dovetail joint* or a *miter joint*?

They are discussing differences in the quality of solutions to a problem. And they avoid getting bogged down in the details of a particular solution

Dovetail Joint

Miter Joint

Their discussion is at a higher level, a more abstract level.

Benefits of Design Patterns

Developer	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• help with design decisions• use of proven solutions of experienced developers• code examples can make it easier to get started• help in passing on and holding on to your own knowledge
Team	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• forming a standardized language• standardized documentation• knowledge transfer between colleagues
Community / Organisation	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• standardized documentation of knowledge• reuse of proven solutions• common structure of systems

Classification of design patterns

Categories

Structural patterns

Creational patterns

Behavioral patterns

Task

Composition of classes and objects

Encapsulation of the creation process of objects

Manage control flows and interactions between classes and objects

Question

Which of the following lines in the core of your application are a violation of the Dependency-Inversion Principle?

- a) `names: List[str] = ["Paul", "John"]`
- b) `circle = Circle(origin, 1)`
- c) both
- d) none

Hint: *The circle class changes frequently*

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A weather station story

Our company creates a popular weather station software. It controls a temperature sensor that measures the temperature every second. Whenever the temperature is measured we want to update a temperature display.

Starting point

The **Application** class contains an instance of the **TemperatureSensor** and a **ConsoleTableChart**. The sensor knows the chart and will call the chart's **draw()** method whenever it measures a new value.

Stage 1: A second chart

Our glorious overlords (managers) have graced us with a new feature request to keep up with the competition: adding a bar chart to the application.

The problem

*In the current state of the application the sensor can only deal with one specific type of chart (**ConsoleTableChart**).*

Stage 2: Mass producing charts

*During the next code review session we show our implementation to our colleagues. They point out that in the Application class we still depend on the concrete chart types **ConsoleTableChart** and **ConsoleBarChart** that change frequently. Also there will be new chart variants in the future so they ask us to improve our solution.*

The solution

Stage 3: Reduce coupling

Our boss informs us that there is still a weakness in our design. Since we will add more charts in the future, we would have to change the interface of the factory each time. Since interfaces should be stable we need to come up with a better solution.

While we are at it we can also implement a feature request from our clients for a menu that allows the users to select a chart type when the application starts.

The problem

*We notice that with our current implementation of the **ChartFactory** the **Application** class still has a dependency to the specific method name of the specific chart we want to create. This means we have to add a method call for every new chart type in our **Application** class. Even worse, this also implies that whenever we need new chart types we have to add a new method to the **ChartFactory** interface, which is also part of our application core. Both are violations of the **Open Closed Principle (OCP)**.*

```
chart = chart_factory.create_table_chart()  
self.sensor.add_chart(chart)
```

```
chart = chart_factory.create_bar_chart()  
self.sensor.add_chart(chart)
```

```
# . . . more to come??
```


Abstract Factory Pattern

- **Object Creational pattern**
- “Intent: Provide an interface for creating families of related or dependent objects without specifying their concrete classes.

* Erich Gamma, Richard Helm, Ralph Johnson, John Vlissides, Design Patterns, 1995

Stage 4: A second sensor

To stay ahead of the competition we decide to add a humidity sensor as a second sensor type to our application. Our boss reassures us that the sensors are known up front and will not be created dynamically at runtime, so no need for an additional factory. However, both sensors need to be able to send updates to a chart.

The problem

*We implement the **HumiditySensor** class and notice that there are some striking similarities to the **TemperatureSensor**.*

The solution

Stage 5: Logging

Our charts have been showing some weird data. To find out what's happening under the hood we want to log the values produced by the sensors to a file.

<https://www.freeimages.com/>

The problem

We need to implement a file logger that is updated along with the charts without implementing the Chart interface.

The solution

Observer Pattern

- **Object Behavioral pattern**
- “Intent: Define a one-to-many dependency between objects so that when objects change state, all its dependents are notified and updated automatically.”*

* Erich Gamma, Richard Helm, Ralph Johnson, John Vlissides, Design Patterns, 1995

Observer

Purpose

1-to-n-Dependencies between Objects: An object can notify all dependent objects

GUI

?

More to come!

volatil

non volatil

Observer

Solution 1

Pull data instead of pushing it

GUI

?

More to come!

volatil

non volatil

Observer

Solution 2

Dependency Inversion

GUI

volatil

More to come!

non volatil

Stage 6: Another strategy

Our clients are complaining again. This time it's the resource consumption of our application. Some of them are using it on very low power machines. Measuring the sensors and updating the charts every second is too much for those tiny CPUs. Some want to have the application only display the data once and then exit, others would like to trigger an update manually and the rest wants to keep the continuous updating we already have.

The problem

We need to implement a mechanism to swap out the behaviour that triggers the measurement. Since some of our clients want to trigger updates manually we can't just set a different timer value.

The solution

*We could have an if statement in the Application's **run()** method to determine when to measure and update our charts. However, that would violate the **Open Closed Principle (OCP)** since we'd have to extend that if statement whenever the requirements for updating change. Instead we decide to apply the **Dependency Inversion Principle (DIP)** and encapsulate the algorithm that determines when we want to call the **measure()** method into different classes that all implement a common interface that we'll call **MeasureStrategy**.*

*When starting our program we inject either a **OneTimeMeasureStrategy**, a **ManualMeasureStrategy** or a **ContinuousMeasureStrategy** into the Application class. Instead of calling the sensor's measure method itself, the Application class will delegate that responsibility to the respective Strategy. We call this the **Strategy Pattern**.*

The solution

Strategy Pattern

- **Object Behavioral pattern**
- “Intent: Define a family of algorithms, encapsulate each one, and make them interchangeable. Strategy lets the algorithm vary independently from clients that use it.”*

* Erich Gamma, Richard Helm, Ralph Johnson, John Vlissides, Design Patterns, 1995

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